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Effect of Drought Stress by Polyethylene Glycol 6000 on Six Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Varieties at Germination and Seedling Stages

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Abstract

Six varieties of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Al-Mokhtar, Margawi, ACSAD901, Casy, Karim, and Salampoo were evaluated under 5 drought levels 0, 60, 120, 180 and 240 g/L (0.00 (control), -0.066, -0.201, -0.407, -0.682 MPa). To make drought stress conditions we used polyethylene glycol (PEG6000). Germinated seeds were counted daily for up to 14 days under laboratory conditions. Germination percentage and mean germination time, coefficients of germination, mean germination rate, and germination index as germination parameters. Seedling, shoot and root length; fresh, dry weight of shoot and root, seedling vigor index, and reduction percentage as seedling growth parameters were studied. Germination and growth of wheat seedling were affected significantly by changes in water stress levels between -4 and -8 MPa. Margawi variety had the highest germination percentage (78%) among the six varieties, followed by Karim. The two varieties of Salampoo and Casy showed the longest mean germination time. We also noticed that Margawi variety was the fastest at the average germination rate, followed by Al-Mukhtar, Karim, and ACSAD 901. The studied varieties showed a clear decrease in all the germination criteria studied at the high drought rates (-0.407 and -0.682 MPa). By studying growth parameters, the variety al-Mokhtar followed by ACSAD 901 and Margawi higher in shoot length; ACSAD 901, Margawi, and Al-Mokhtar sequentially in plant length.

Keywords: drought stress, water stress, germination, wheat, PEG 6000, osmotic stress

INTRODUCTION

Approximately 25% of agricultural lands are affected by environmental stress around the world. Thus, agricultural productivity is subject to crop failure and average yields lose more than 50% (Fathi and Tari, 2016). Drought is one of the abiotic stresses that affect the growth and development of plants under water deficit conditions. Drought stress is one of the most limiting factors especially in warm dry areas yielding crops. (Qadir, 2019). Two stages are critical for optimum plant growth and development, at planting and the reproductive stages (Rasaei *et al.*, 2013). Germination is one of the main growth stages for seedling establishment, and success in this stage is dependent on moisture availability in the soil (Partheeban *et al.*, 2017). The effect of drought on the yield of the crops depends on the severity and stage of plant growth during which it occurs. The first stage of growth (seed germination) is sensitive to water deficit (Khakwani *et al.*, 2011; Xiaoyu *et al.*, 2014). According to Ashraf and Mahmood (1990), the most sensitive stage in the life cycle of plants is the germination stage. Perfect, rapid, and uniform germination is essential to having a good green area and crop growth rate that will get better fluorescence and increase the yield (Ashraf & Mahmood, 1990).

Seedling growth is influenced by drought stress according to the varieties. Wheat production will increase if the varieties with the best performance under water stress conditions were selected (Ahmad *et al.*, 2013; Abro *et al.*,

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2020). As a suitable growth stage to prove wheat adaptability under osmotic stress conditions, the seedling development stage under laboratory conditions has been accepted.

To assess the effects on germination and seedling of wheat, and to explore the plant adaptation ability and response, many osmotic solutions were used (Razmjoo *et al.*, 2015; Chaniago *et al.*, 2017). Using polyethylene glycol 6000 (PEG₆₀₀₀) accepted as a suitable method to efficiently test large sets of germplasm with good rigor. PEG is recognized as an inert, non-penetrating, non-ionic, and high molecular weight. It can lower the water potential of nutrient solutions without passing or being phytotoxic (Khakwani *et al.*, 2011; Qadir, 2019) and without causing any significant physiological damage to crop plants (Khakwani *et al.*, 2011; Hellal *et al.*, 2018). The advantage of using PEG₆₀₀₀ compared to other osmotic solutions (easily taken by the cell) is that it cannot enter the cell. The water is outgoing from the cell without affecting the cell structure (Ahmad *et al.*, 2017). PEG₆₀₀₀ is used by many researchers to study the ability of different wheat genotypes to tolerate drought stress (Ahmad *et al.*, 2017; Kacem *et al.*, 2017; Hellal *et al.*, 2018; Abro *et al.*, 2020) at different concentrations (osmotic pressure). The objectives of the current study were to compare the ability of six wheat genotypes to tolerate drought stress using PEG-6000 at the germination stage and seedling growth characteristics of six wheat varieties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To study the effects of drought stress, using polyethylene glycol, on the germination stage and seedling growth characteristics of wheat, the experiment was conducted in the Department of Plant Production, Faculty of Agriculture-Soluq/ University of Benghazi, Libya. The form of the experiment was a factorial (varieties and stress levels), a completely randomized design with five replications.

Seeds of six wheat varieties (Al- Mokhtar, Margawi, ACSAD 901, Casy, Karim, and Salampoo) were used. These varieties were obtained from the Agricultural Research Center of Misurata- Libya were all obtained from CIMMYT. Wheat seeds were subjected to five stress levels of polyethylene glycol (PEG₆₀₀₀) (ACROS, company); 0, 60, 120, 180 and 240 g/L, (0.00, -0.066, -0.201, -0.407 and -0.682 MPa) respectively, were prepared according to Michel and Kaufmann equation $\{[OP = (-1.18 \times 10^{-2}) \times C - (1.18 \times 10^{-4}) \times C + (2.67 \times 10^{-4}) \times C \times T + (8.39 \times 10^{-7}) \times C^2 T]\}$; where OP= water osmotic potential (Bar); C=PEG concentration (g/Kg); T=temperature (°C)} (Kaufmann and Eckard, 1971); (Michel and Kaufmann, 1973). PEG₆₀₀₀ was prepared by dissolving the required amount in distilled water at 30°C. Wheat grains were disinfected with 5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution for 3 minutes. Then seeds were washed three times with distilled water. 20 grains from each variety were distributed on two layers of filter paper in plastic Petri dishes (90-mm in diameter), filter papers (Whatman No.2) were moistened with 10 ml of treatments from PEG₆₀₀₀. Petri dishes were covered and sealed with parafilm to prevent evaporation of moisture (Emmerich and Hardegree, 1991) and incubated under laboratory conditions (27±2 °C) for 14 days.

Seeds were considered germinated when exhibited radicle extension was >2 mm. Every 24 hours germinated seeds were counted daily during the experiment to determine the following germination parameters: *germination percentage (G %)*, *mean germination time (MGT)*, *coefficient of variation (CVi)*, *mean germination rate (MGR)*, and *germination index (GI)* (Ranal and Santana, 2006).

Germination percentage (G %) = (germinated seeds/total seeds) × 100 (Španić *et al.*, 2017); (Surbhaiyya *et al.*, 2018); *mean germination time (MGT)* = $\sum Dn / \sum n$ (where n is the number of seeds, which were germinated on day D, and D is the number of days counted from the beginning of germination) (Dezfuli *et al.*, 2008); *coefficient of variation (CVi)* = $\sum Ni / \sum NiTi \times 100$ (Almaghrabi, 2012); *mean germination rate (MGR)* the reciprocal of the mean germination time (Ranal *et al.*, 2009); *germination index (GI)* = [(germination percentage in each PEG₆₀₀₀ level/ germination percentage in 0 MPa) × 100] (Ahmed *et al.*, 2019).

The experiment was terminated 14 days after seed soaking and traits, harvesting seedlings were measured to obtain: [*shoot length*, *root length*, *seedling length*, *seedling fresh weight*, *shoot fresh weight*, *root fresh weight*, *shoot dry weight*, *root dry weight*, *seedling vigor index (SVi)*, and *reduction percentage (R%)*] (Ahmadloo *et al.*, 2011; Razmjoo *et al.*, 2015). All of these calculations were organized in an Excel sheet according to (Ranal and Santana, 2006). *Shoot length (ShL)*, *root length (RL)*, and *seedling length (SL)* were measured by rubber

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centimeter. *seedling fresh weight (SFW)*, *shoot fresh weight (ShFW)*, *root fresh weight (RFW)*, *shoot dry weight (ShDW)*, and *root dry weight (RDW)* were measured in weight in grams with an electronic digital balance for fresh weight, then dried in a hot air oven at 80°C for 24 h and weighed again for dry weight, and *seedling vigor index (SVi)* = [seedling length (cm) × germination percentage] (Ahmed et al., 2019). *Reduction percentage (R%)* = (value under each PEG₆₀₀₀ level - value under 0 MPa) (Farshadfar et al., 2012).

Experimental design and statistical analysis

The effects of two factors were analyzed in these experiments and a completely randomized design with five replicates of 20 seeds per replicate. The first factor (Wheat varieties) had six levels (Al- Mokhtar, Margawi, ACSAD 901, Casy, Karim, and Salampoo). The second factor (OP – Drought levels) had five levels 0, 60, 120, 180 and 240 g/L (0.0, -0.066, -0.201, -0.407, and -0.682 MPa). The data were analyzed statistically using IBM SPSS statistics software ver. 23, 2015). Analyses of variance (ANOVA) of the obtained data was applied to identify significant differences among wheat varieties and treatments. The least significant difference test was applied at a five percent level of probability to comparisons among means (Steel and Torrie, 1980).

RESULTS

In this study, six varieties of wheat were tested to determine their response to artificial drought conditions using PEG₆₀₀₀ at a different level of concentrations.

PEG₆₀₀₀ has been used in experiments to provide controlled experimental conditions in terms of water potential and to study the negative effects of water stress created on seed germination and early seedling growth stages. Five levels of artificial stress, using PEG₆₀₀₀, were used in this experiment for an in vitro environment.

The results were as noted in Table 1 shows the effects of varieties (Var), drought stress (T), and their interaction of them (Var*T) were significant for *G %*, *GI*, *MGT*, and *MGR*. the *CVi* is not significant for the variety and the interaction Var*T.

Table 1. Analyses of variance for germination traits of wheat varieties under different drought levels

Source	df	Germination Percentage (G%)	Germination Index (GI)	Mean Germination Time (MGT)	Coefficient of Variation (CVi)	Mean Germination Rate (MGR)
Var	5	5076.40 *	6717.43 *	6.43 *	648.23 ^{ns}	0.135 *
T	4	18721.00 *	31030.15 *	10.92 *	5622.98 *	0.149 *
Var * T	20	925.40 *	1528.59 *	4.57 *	399.13 ^{ns}	0.019 *
Error	120	214.000	1168.675	1.034	300.335	0.005

ns, not significant. * Significance at 0.01 and 0.05 % levels of probability. *df*: a degree of freedom.

A negative effect difference was observed between all studied genotypes of all germination traits as shown in (Figures 1-5), indicating potential genetic variation in response to the simulated drought stress of PEG₆₀₀₀.

Data are relevant to the effect of the simulated drought stress reaction induced by PEG₆₀₀₀ levels and wheat varieties during germination, as shown in (Figure 1).

The results showed that the highest germination rate was at the first and second levels of drought levels, while the lowest germination percentage was at the fifth level (240 g/L). and the Margawi variety was the highest among all varieties, followed by the Karim variety, while the rest of the varieties were equal, noting the overlap among the workers, we note that the germination rate decreased in all varieties with an increase in the concentration of PEG₆₀₀₀. Germination speed decreased with increased PEG₆₀₀₀ osmotic pressure.

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Fig. 1. Effect of drought stress on germination percentage of six-wheat varieties

Fig. 2. Effect of drought stress on mean germination time of six-wheat varieties

Fig. 3. Effect of drought stress on the coefficient of variation of six-wheat varieties

On the other hand, the highest germination index value (Figure 4) was observed for Al-Mokhtar genotype at all levels of the PEG₆₀₀₀. These results confirmed that the degree of reduction was not the same for all wheat genotypes studied under the studied PEG₆₀₀₀ levels.

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From Table 2, the results of the analysis of variance exhibited the presence of a considerable genotypic variation among the genotypes ($P \leq 0.01$ & 0.05), indicating the possibility of discriminating drought-tolerant landraces in the field conditions significant. Differences were observed between all parameters of the seedling stage, whether at the level of varieties or the level of treatments. Also, their interaction (Var*T). Except for the percentage of seedling relative tolerance and reduction percentage at the level of Var*T.

From Table 3 and figures (6-8), the higher the PEG₆₀₀₀ the lower the length of both the shoot and root as well as the seedling length. The varieties Al-Mukhtar, Margawi, and ACSAD 901 were the most tolerant of drought conditions at the first three drought levels (0.0, 60, and 120g/L). Genotypes differed in the length of the seedlings under different levels of PEG₆₀₀₀. The highest shoot length of al-Mokhtar followed by ACSAD and Margawi at 0.0, 60g/L. for root length, the six varieties were divided into two clusters in their response (Fig.7) to drought levels (Margawi and ACSAD), (Al-Mokhtar, Casy, Karim, and Salampoo).

Table 2. Analysis of variance for seedling traits of wheat varieties under different drought levels.

Source	df	mean square						
		Shoot Length <i>ShL</i> (cm.)	Root Length <i>RL</i> (cm.)	Seedling Length <i>SL</i> (cm.)	Seedling Fresh Weight <i>SFW</i> (g)	Reduction seedling length Percentage <i>R%SL</i>	Reduction seedling fresh weight Percentage <i>R%SFW</i>	Vigor Index <i>Vi</i>
Var.	5	122.93 *	78.69 *	317.54 *	0.028 *	3712670.29 *	198.75 *	14.17 *
T	4	635.15 *	376.62 *	1994.95 *	0.083 *	23082626.7 *	946.02 *	68.05 *
Var. * T	20	9.94 *	28.74 *	53.53 *	0.003 *	466164.18 ns	31.35 ns	2.89 *
Error	120	3.55	9.75	20.49	0.001	394853.40	22.99	0.72

ns, not significant. * Significance at 0.01 and 0.05 % levels of probability. *df*: a degree of freedom.

The fresh weight of the seedlings was negatively affected by the increase of drought levels in all wheat varieties. Figure 9. shows that the maximum seedling fresh weight was observed in Al-Mukhtar and ACSAD 901 at 0.0, 60, and 120g/L. Casy and Karim varieties were the most affected by the increase in drought level their response was the lowest.

The vigor index expresses the speed of germination (Fig.10) found higher at 0.0, 60g/L for Margawi genotype, and Al-Mokhtar, with no significant difference between the four varieties (Al-Mokhtar, ACSAD 901, Casy, and Karim). The degree of reduction of seedling length and fresh weight was not similar for wheat varieties and a higher level of PEG₆₀₀₀ drought.

Fig. 4. Effect of drought stress on the mean germination rate of six-wheat varieties

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Fig. 5. Effect of drought stress on the germination index of six-wheat varieties

Fig. 6. Effect of drought stress on the shoot length of six-wheat variety under drought stress stimulated by PEG₆₀₀₀

Fig. 7. Effect of drought stress on the root length of six-wheat variety under drought stress stimulated by PEG₆₀₀₀

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Fig. 8. Effect of drought stress on the seedling length of six-wheat variety under drought stress stimulated by PEG₆₀₀₀

Table 3. Mean comparison of seedling wheat variety traits under different drought levels.

Variety	ShL	RL	SL	SFW	R%SL	R%SFW	Vi
<i>Al- Mokhtar</i>	10.72 ± 4.983 a	10.52 ± 2.692 b	21.01 ± 6.40 a	0.137 ± 0.086 a	- 659.7 ± 662.07 b	- 2.43 ± 8.73 ab	2.179 ± 1.29 e
<i>Margawi</i>	8.89 ± 4.439 bc	13.55 ± 5.001 a	22.15 ± 9.122 a	0.099 ± 0.045 b	- 940 ± 991.39 bc	- 5.01 ± 5.42 bc	3.846 ± 2.06 b
<i>ACSAD 901</i>	9.18 ± 5.542 b	12.76 ± 4.677 a	22.05 ± 9.939 a	0.123 ± 0.077 a	- 948.83 ± 1060.7 bc	- 9.38 ± 7.85 d	2.488 ± 1.945b
<i>Casy</i>	5.52 ± 4.234 d	9.03 ± 4.930 b	14.10 ± 9.676 c	0.065 ± 0.050 c	- 1133 ± 967.54 c	- 7.02 ± 4.84 cd	2.123 ± 1.925b
<i>Karim</i>	5.01 ± 3.436 d	9.87 ± 4.157 b	15.04 ± 6.833 c	0.049 ± 0.034 c	- 238.13 ± 804.01 a	- 1.68 ± 4.28 a	2.254 ± 1.345b
<i>Salampoo</i>	7.84 ± 5.189 c	9.95 ± 6.307 b	17.99 ± 10.78 b	0.094 ± 0.069 b	- 57.04 ± 1370.70 c	- 1.84 ± 9.02 a	1.632 ± 1.464c
<i>L.S.D</i>	1.055	1.749	2.535	0.0211	394.435	3.01	0.476
Stress level g/L							
<i>0 g/L</i>	11.930 ± 3.183 A	12.109 ± 4.367 B	24.03 ± 6.20 A	0.131 ± 0.053AB	-	-	3.774 ± 1.63A
<i>60 g/L</i>	11.700 ± 2.600 A	13.852 ± 3.041 A	25.57 ± 4.107A	0.142 ± 0.066A	153.97 ± 614.48 A	1.07 ± 5.89 A	3.814 ± 1.22A
<i>120 g/L</i>	8.866 ± 4.114 B	12.52 ± 4.844 AB	21.42 ± 8.445 B	0.114 ± 0.066B	- 260.59 ± 863.18 B	- 1.75 ± 6.23 B	2.619 ± 1.47B
<i>180 g/L</i>	5.907 ± 2.739 C	11.38 ± 3.382 B	17.36 ± 5.289 C	0.075 ± 0.035C	- 666.32 ± 679.49 C	- 5.66 ± 4.94 C	1.627 ± 0.96C
<i>240 g/L</i>	0.892 ± 1.195 D	4.80 ± 3.245 C	5.24 ± 4.675D	0.012 ± 0.018D	- 1879.09 ± 777.15 D	- 11.90 ± 5.36 D	0.269 ± 0.38D
<i>L.S.D</i>	0.963	1.597	2.3141	0.0193	322.0545	2.4574	0.4344

Means in a column followed by different letters are significantly different at p = 0.05; (Small letters difference between varieties, capital letters between treatments)

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Fig. 9. Effect of drought stress on the seedling fresh weight of six-wheat variety under drought stress stimulated by PEG₆₀₀₀

Fig. 10. Effect of drought stress on the vigor index of six-wheat variety under drought stress stimulated by PEG₆₀₀₀

Genotypes were also different for indicators of drought tolerance, such as percentage reduction (R %) for seedling length and fresh weight (Fig. 11 & 12).

Fig. 11. Effect of drought stress on the reduction seedling length percentage of six-wheat variety under drought stress stimulated by PEG₆₀₀₀

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Fig. 12. Effect of drought stress on the reduction seedling fresh weight percentage of six-wheat variety under drought stress stimulated by PEG₆₀₀₀

The highest reduction percentage of seedling length was for the Casy variety, and we observed that increasing the drought level increased the reduction length percentage. Acsad901 was the highest variety showed a higher reduction in fresh weight percentage when compared to the 0.00 level of drought. Increasing the PEG₆₀₀₀ had a clear effect on seedling fresh weight

Al-Mokhtar and Salampoo classes did not show a decrease in the average fresh weight at the level (0.0, 60g/L). The rest of the varieties showed a clear decrease in the average fresh weight. The Salamppoo variety showed resistance to the effect of drought on seedling length at the level of (0.0, 60g/L) and Karim at the control level. The other varieties showed a gradual decrease in length and fresh weight with increasing drought levels. These results cleared that the degree of reduction was not similar for considered all wheat genotypes at the levels of PEG₆₀₀₀.

DISCUSSION

In this study, the ability of six wheat varieties under chemical drought induced by PEG₆₀₀₀ was studied during germination and the early seedling stage under laboratory conditions. The seed germination percentage at the control level was highest and started to decrease as the osmotic stress level was increased. These results are in agreement with those reported by (Gholamin *et al.*, 2010; Almaghrabi, 2012; Chachar *et al.*, 2014; Chachar *et al.*, 2016; Ahmed *et al.*, 2019). Osmotic stress reduces the potential gradient of water between seeds and their environment, so Dodd and Donovan (1999) have reported that it can cause seed germination to decrease. Increasing the concentration of drought level reduces the length of the shoot and root of all studied wheat varieties. The deficiency in the growth of the shoot and roots was previously recorded by Ahmed *et al.*, (2019); Abro *et al.*, (2020) under conditions of water pressure. Osmotic stress reduces seed germination and seedling growth under osmotic stress conditions (Surbhaiyya *et al.*, 2018).

Drought tolerance is a developmentally regulated phenomenon, which is a specific stage, depending on the genetic pattern of wheat and the severity of stress applied. PEG is the best to impose a low water pressure that reflects the type of stress imposed by dry soil. Since water is one of the basic requirements for seed germination (Shaban, 2013), the water stress developed by PEG reduces seed germination capacity. Germination of wheat slower under osmotic water pressure caused by PEG due to insufficient surface contact of water with seeds, seed size (Demir & Mavi, 2008), and surface coating properties of seeds (Mohammadi and Mojaddam, 2014), which restricts water availability for seeds (Khan *et al.*, 2013).

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The development of seedlings under laboratory conditions was accepted as an appropriate growth stage for drought tolerance testing in wheat. It can be assumed that increased concentrations of PEG during seedling growth prevent growth characteristics and the survival of wheat seedlings. Casy and Karim were the most affected by increasing the drought level (fig. 6-8). While the length of the shoot has always been reduced by exposure to all levels of stress-tested, there has been an increase in the root length associated with the treatment of 120g/L PEG for the Salampoo and al-Mokhtar varieties. Other varieties tolerated drought conditions by increasing the length of the roots to obtain water at the first three drought levels (0, 60, and 120g/L). One of the reasons for the decrease in the shoot and root lengths under drought stress conditions could be the lack of transfer of nutrients from the storage tissues of the seeds into the embryo, could be associated with the fact that meristem cells of the root and shoot are affected and the cell division and elongation process are disrupted. (Mohammadi and Mojaddam, 2014). Therefore, a decrease in the length of the seedlings under osmotic water pressure results from the inhibition of cell division and elongation (Kamran *et al.*, 2009; Chachar *et al.*, 2016). An increase in the PEG₆₀₀₀ osmotic pressure level not only prevents germination properties but also impedes the growth of stretching of seedlings (Rana *et al.*, 2017). Water stress PEG₆₀₀₀ also reduced the use of seed reserves and the dissolution of sugars (Harb, 2013).

Increased levels of PEG₆₀₀₀ caused a decrease in the fresh and dry weight of the seedlings is due to the lower growth of seedlings. Chachar *et al.* (2016) reported that the potential osmotic resistance of PEG₆₀₀₀ was taken into account by the small limit of seedling growth under conditions of induced stress PEG₆₀₀₀. Therefore, fresh and dry weight seedlings are very important attributes when selecting potential tolerant genotypes of osmotic water (Surbhaiyya *et al.*, 2018). The declining trend in seedlings of fresh and dry weight has been reported by many other scientists (Chachar *et al.*, 2014; Ahmad *et al.*, 2017; Baque *et al.*, 2018), they found that water stress had a significant negative impact on seedlings in fresh and dry weight.

CONCLUSION

The six wheat varieties were grown with PEG₆₀₀₀ treatments under in-vitro conditions. The results of the research showed that drought stress treatment had a significant effect on germination traits, including germination percentage, mean daily germination, coefficient of the velocity of germination, mean germination rate, germination index, root length, shoot length, seedling length and seed vigor and led to a decrease. Generally, different levels of drought stress had a significant effect on all measured traits at the 12 – 24% (120-240g/L) level. In this experiment, Margawi and al-Mokhtar were the highest tolerance varieties. Had acceptable germination percentage under drought stress of 0.00 to 120 g/L, which indicates the characteristics of Margawi and Al-Mokhtar in tolerating drought stress and suitable for cultivation in arid and semiarid areas. Considering the varieties, it can be said that under drought stress of 60g/L, the highest germination percentage belonged to Margawi variety and the lowest germination percentage belonged to the Salampoo variety. In summary, owing to its better growth responses to stress conditions. Studying shoot /root fresh weight and shoot/ root dry weight; Margawi followed by Al-Mokhtar and Acsad901 was the highest rate at the first three levels of drought, also for the vigor index, which expresses the speed of germination.

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